

BIODIVERSITY WITHIN GÜLLÜK GULF, THREATS THE ECOSYSTEM FACES DUE TO HIGH EUTROPHICATION RATES AND POLLUTION - RECOMMENDATIONS TO STOP AND REVERSE THE CURRENT STATE OF DEGRADATION

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Abstract

This white paper details the results of a 3-year monitoring project in Güllük Gulf, in southwestern Türkiye, between 2007-2010, during which sensitive and endangered taxa were identified with assistance of several scientists, and a final policy paper was formulated. Beginning of the monitoring project coincided with the introduction of a notification by the Ministry of Environment, in which parameters were specified (depth, distance from shore, minimum current speed, turbidity, etc.) for closed and semi-closed gulfs where aquaculture practices were to be established. The parameters that were declared with this legal notice were critical as they put several fragile marine ecosystems on a list of suitable places to establish aquaculture farms. This alerted the general public of the coastal towns where the practices were already hurting the marine ecosystems through excessive pollution, desertification of the sea floor, and degradation of quality of seawater overall. Güllük Gulf stood in a different segment, as the gulf harbored high levels of biodiversity, and several endangered taxa that were under protection by international conventions.

Photo 1. İnceburun, a typical shoreline formation within the Güllük Gulf. (Photo by Bikem Ekberzade)

Current Situation

Situated at 37° 12' 59" N and 27° 31' 39" E, and northwest of the Gökova Gulf protected zone (and a biodiversity hotspot), Güllük Gulf inhabits similar if not higher levels species diversity within its two inner gulfs of Mandalya and Asin (list of observed taxa between 2008-2010 are provided in Annex A). Its basin is home to endangered species, some endemic, others migratory, and most of which are under protection by several international conventions. The gulf consists of several different habitats (fishing weir, wetland, lagoon, etc.). Both the marine and the terrestrial area in and around the gulf bear a heavy human footprint, with the lands surrounding used for agriculture, specifically olive cultivation, for hundreds of years. Despite continuous anthropogenic interference, the coastal ecosystems still harbor forests, home to mainly *Pinus brutia*, *P. halepensis* and maquis commonly found in Mediterranean climate-type ecosystems (*Quercus coccifera* in shrub form, *Q. ilex*, *Juniperus* spp., etc.). Although the marine habitat, with its numerous small coves, has been greatly disturbed especially during the past 15+ years due to uncontrolled aquaculture practices which devastated the surrounding coastal areas with high levels of pollutants (excess organic waste as well as common trash), biodiversity in the untouched areas both within the marine basin and on land persevered (personal observation).

In recent years, complaints on the nature of the aquaculture practices led the Ministry of Environment to issue a notification (*Denizlerde Balık Çiftliklerinin Kurulamayacağı Hassas Alan Niteliğindeki Kapalı Koy ve Körfez Alanlarının Belirlenmesine İlişkin Tebliğ (Resmi Gazete #26413, 24.01.2007)*). The legal paper set a number of baseline parameters for "sensitive gulfs" (direct translation: closed or semi-closed gulfs which harbor qualities that may classify them as sensitive) where aquaculture practices can be undertaken as long as they meet the following criteria:

1. Minimum depth for the cages to be set should not be less than 30 m. (aiming to eliminate shallow gulf areas as potential farm areas),
2. Minimum current speed cannot be less than 0.1 m/sec (aiming to eliminate stagnant areas),
3. Minimum distance to land cannot be less than 0,6 nautical miles (aiming to protect the coasts from any potential negative effects).

One other parameter which the notification mentions is eutrophication: a number 4 on the TRIX index are considered suitable for cultivation, and any number between 4 and 6 indicate a risk towards eutrophication. Any number above 6 depicts a eutrophic marine zone, where all potential polluting practices should be stopped. As can be foreseen by the relatively low parameters for depth, speed of current, as well as distance to land, the negative impacts of aquaculture practices on sensitive ecosystems would be quick to show themselves, as we now see in Güllük Gulf. More specifically throughout the Asin Gulf, which is by nature a shallower basin resting on the coastal shelf, with a complex current regime, (*TUBİTAK-METU report: Muğla Kıyılarında Koyları Etkilemeyecek Deniz Balığı Yetiştirme Alanlarının Tespiti, TUBİTAK-ODTÜ, September 2005, pages 132-133, 162-163*) eutrophication that can regularly be observed in its coves have spread throughout the inner gulf as the cages are now set in its center.

This white paper aims to explain why the limitations posed in these parameters are not enough, and while they do set certain standards for aquaculture practices, they still lack the protection potential when closed and semi-closed gulfs that harbor high levels of biodiversity are concerned.

A shallow inner gulf: Asin

Asin Gulf is one of the two connected inner gulfs of the greater Gulluk Gulf. Asin itself is shallow, with its deepest part, around approximately 30 m around its southwesterly entrance. The current regime varies according to the changing meteorological and oceanographic conditions, with the main current entering from the relatively wide northwesterly entrance (~7 nm wide), and travelling within the gulf in a complex pattern. The current speeds within Asin Gulf are especially slow along the shores. And due to the positioning and the width of this inner gulf's opening (little more than 2 nm), inner waters not able to refresh at a fast rate (*Muğla Kıyılarında Koyları Etkilemeyecek Deniz Balığı Yetiştirme Alanlarının Tespiti, TUBİTAK-ODTÜ, Eylül 2005, sayfa: 132-133, 162-163*). Wind patterns in southwest Turkey are mainly northerly, with occasional strong, hurricane level northeasterly gusts. They encourage surface flow, however do not affect much the gulf's inner dynamics, ameliorating eutrophication within the gulf as a whole (Fig. 1).

Within Asin, the rest of the seafloor is relatively high, with average depth around 23 m. and less. This alone makes the area risky for any aquaculture practice with a potential to increase eutrophication, as debris from the cages directly subside, building up on the seafloor. However, both due to its shallow nature and the hydrothermal vents in the basin, temperature of the sea water is warmer in Asin than in other parts of the Güllük Gulf. These warmer waters allow coralline formations to appear throughout the inner gulf, and which also makes this delicate natural habitat a prime spot for the fish farms as growth is faster in protected warm waters.

As can be seen in the underwater photos 2a and b, the water is already starting to show signs of eutrophication, with visible hanging matter (feces, washed out feed from the cages, micro plastics, etc.). These turbid gulf waters also encourage algae blooms, where algae, reproducing rapidly, covering the outer surfaces of *Posidonia ocanica* shoots and corals, lower their photosynthesis ability, at times smothering them. This in turn leads coral bleaching, and mass dieback in *P. ocanica* grasslands.

Figure 1. Varying maximum depths (shown in ft.) within Asin Gulf, within the greater Güllük Gulf.

Photo 2. Schools of fish, and the water showing signs of eutrophication, Mandalya side (left), hanging matter on the Asin side over a healthy patch of *P. ocanica* (right). (Photos by Bikem Ekberzade)

Güllük Gulf

Güllük Gulf is typical of most Aegean-Mediterranean coastlines, with sharp inclines of rocky formations continuing well onto the sea floor (Photo 1). Thus, Mediterranean shrubs, and other plants endemic to these rocky shores become extremely important in preventing erosion during the rainy months in the winter, spring and fall. In the rainy seasons, precipitation events can be extreme, causing flooding around riverbeds, and heavy runoff to the sea in steep inclines unless the rootzone is present to provide slope stability. Floods that occur around the gulf with heavy runoff to the sea at times saturate the gulf with sediment rich in organic matter, topsoil rich in seeds and other nutrients, contributing to the eutrophic nature of the inner gulfs. In recent years, construction projects around the gulf area has disrupted the delicate and important shrublands, replacing them with cement structures and asphalt roads. These all contributed to an increase in runoff, further endangering the delicate ecosystems within the Güllük Gulf.

Figure 2. Land use land cover change around Asin Gulf between 1990 (left) and 2008 (right). (Google Earth captures)

Thus, exposed to such continuous anthropogenic pressures, a gulf such as Güllük with its several endangered species, should be protected by means of a special status granted by the relevant administrations. Instead, caught in a crossfire between rampant urbanization and aquaculture practices, it is left to its own devices. Although Güllük Gulf is not a sustainable site of choice for culture fish farming, in its current state, excess feed and feces from the large populations of seabass and seabream continuously pumping organic nutrients to an already overloaded, eutrophic marine environment, continue to cause uninterrupted disturbance to the sensitive sessile species such as corals and *P. ocanica* beds in the gulf. The quality of the sea water is adversely affected, visibility from

high turbidity falling under 1 meter in places, blocking sunlight and limiting the filtering and the photosynthesis capacities of the species. Dropping oxygen levels, both due to the inevitable desertification on the sea floor and decomposition processes using whatever available oxygen is there to break up the excess waste, is ending life in the deeper parts of the photic zone, where sunlight can hardly by now hardly penetrate. This may be a desired result for the corporations investing in the gulf as an aquaculture strong spot, as with the annihilation of the endangered species, and loss of biodiversity, an immediate protection status for the gulf will not be granted. However, from a sustainability perspective, this is indeed something that will also hurt their investments in the long run, as the gulf's TRIX index exceeds the threshold, all production will forcibly be stopped by the legal administrations.

Posidonia oceanica, the sea grass rightfully named "lungs of the Mediterranean", is under protection by the Barcelona Convention of 1995, to which Turkey is a signatory. The fact that the species' livelihood is directly and adversely affected by the drift from the cages that are set up in dangerous proximity to the underwater meadows, has also been widely documented by the METU scientific study of 2003 (pg.101,104-105, 133-134). These adverse results can also be observed today. In an era in which ecosystems are already battling with the negative outcomes of global warming (i.e. desertification), for us to stand idly by and watch the disappearance of at least two endangered and sensitive species with the ability of photosynthesis, due to procedural errors of human intervention, especially when needs are compared against necessities, is hardly acceptable.

International organizations such as the NOAA, WRI and IUCN have also confirmed the destruction of the coralline species and the *Posidonia* meadows, through extensive sharing and exchange of information from the site in question. These organizations have also called for urgent precautions to be taken to stop further destruction of the meadows within the Gulf, all suggestions unfortunately falling to deaf ears both on the production and on the protection side. The words of Dr. Steve Gittings, a coral expert at the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Association are especially worthy of note:

"Reversing the problem requires aggressive measures that result in improvements in water quality. Moving the aquaculture facilities is probably one requirement. They should not be close to the coral habitat and should not be upstream. When deciding where to locate them, current patterns need to be considered, as you suggest, and they should be in an area that does not take the waste stream toward the coral communities."

In line with the METU report (pg. 162-163), the corals are under threat of the deposits from the aquaculture cages, as the current regime in Asin Gulf is mainly from the northwesterly with the debris being washed eastward, or in simpler terms, from the mouth of the gulf towards the southern shores, carrying all the debris from the cages to the rocky shallow basin on the shore. The corals hanging on to the rocks along the coastal shelf are thus directly affected by the excess organic waste, as well as the overpopulation of invasive species such as *Jania rubensis*, which in turn cling to the corals' prickly surface, further suffocating them. Losing their ability for photosynthesis, the corals, some of which have been formed slowly over half a century or more, are defenseless to the algae which cover them up, speeding their calcification and gradual death in a matter of weeks.

Again, to quote the words of Dr. Steve Gittings:

"Regardless of the cause (for example, aquaculture, inadequately treated sewage, runoff from agricultural facilities, uncontrolled coastal development), nutrients typically promote the growth of leafy and filamentous algae, resulting in the competition for space on reefs. Algae usually wins the battle over corals, which grow very slowly. Algae also allows sediments to accumulate, forming what are sometimes called "algae-sediment mats." The soft surface resulting from this process inhibits coral growth and further accelerates their mortality. Thus corals like the one you photographed, which may take 10-50 years to grow, must compete against algae that can grow in a matter of weeks or months."

Photo 3. Coral bleaching, southern coastline of Asin Gulf, 2008-2010. (Photos by Bikem Ekberzade)

In a similar fashion, the *Posidonia* meadows are also adversely affected from the organic overload in the sea water. Dr. Ferit Bingel, the joint-author of the above mentioned METU report details as such: "One of the factors limiting the expansion of *Posidonia oenica* on our shores is the aquaculture practices set up either on, or close to the meadows." He continues to stress the fact that the excess feed and feces from the cages:

"increase the organic load in the water. In addition the salinity (nutrient) is increased leading to overload (eutrophication) The hanging matter in the water decreases visibility, blocking the essential light for photosynthesis from reaching the meadows. Furthermore, the debris from the cages sink to the sea bottom before having the chance to break down, thus covering the surfaces of the *Posidonia* shoots, killing them... The meadows, deprived from essential light for photosynthesis, thus shrink in tandem with the increase in organic pollution. It is worthy of note that the space, closest to the production areas, thus emptied as with the death of the sea grass, is in turn taken over by an invasive species: *Caulerpa racemosa*." (TUBİTAK-ODTÜ, pg. 101)

Photo 4. *Caulerpa racemosa* ve *Jania rubenis*. (Photos by Bikem Ekberzade).

In the above mentioned METU report, Prof. Ferit Bingel and team recorded the below observation during their extensive analysis of the Güllük Gulf in 2003:

“Within Güllük Gulf where aquaculture practices are densely present, a similar habitat loss has been seen as such around Ziraat Island and Bozburun. Hanging matter density has seriously increased and transparency has starkly diminished while the meadows have been completely obliterated. Where aquaculture farming has recently started around Salih Island, whereas the length of meadow leaves and the density of new shoots are low, the meadow extends to under 20 meters. In this area, *Pinna nobilis*, a species under protection, has been encountered in large numbers. Also in Alagün and Kazıklı, both of which have a short history of farming, although the meadows extend to depth below 20 meters, the deterioration in leaf length and the lower density of new shoots, shows us the pressure the meadows are under.” (*TUBİTAK-ODTÜ*, pg. 104-105).

When Bingel and team's observations of 2004 are compared to the study they conducted the previous year, there is ample proof that the wildlife in the region is under direct threat from organic pollution to which the aquaculture practices directly contribute to (*TUBİTAK-ODTÜ*, pg. 105). As of today, we know that the current placement of the cages are either directly above or very near to *Posidonia* meadows. And as you can see in Photo 4, the meadows are adversely affected from aquaculture-caused organic pollution. The METU report clearly states the potential threat from aquaculture practices which the meadows are under (*TUBİTAK-ODTÜ*, pg. 101, 104-105, 133-134). As we now can tangibly observe the results of global warming, the annihilation of taxa that hold a critical role for carbon sequestration, by otherwise preventable anthropogenic stressors, on a needs-necessities scale has to be urgently reconsidered.

Yet, unfortunately, during May-June of 2010, new cages were transferred to new spots within Asin Gulf. Despite all our warnings towards the existing sensitive/endangered species in the region, Muğla Agriculture and Village Works Directorate declared that the current placements are legal and that there are 80 more such points within the Gulf that have been designated as aquaculture production sites. When all the designated nodes are covered with cages and full production begins, the current organic pollution in the Gulf will quadruple by best case scenario. When we look at the accelerated destruction of *Posidonia* meadows within the last year, the enlarged aquatic farmland will seriously hinder the wildlife and biological diversity in the area.

Photo 5. Barren patches where the *P. oenica* has died and empty patches were taken over by invasive species. (Photos by Bikem Ekberzade).

As Bingel also mentions in his report, immediately following the new placement of the cages in the middle portion of Asin Gulf, the meadows and *Pinna nobilis* populations both showed signs of retreating, whereas common species have taken over the places vacated by more sensitive ones. The fragile species sensitive to the stressors within the gulf largely disappeared, as they lost the battle for space and oxygen due to pollution and eutrophication to their stronger counterparts.

Photo 6. Güllük Gulf, Çam (Pine) cove (left); cages in Asin (right). (Photos by Bikem Ekberzade).

Through rigorous observation and monitoring through skin dives, several species, listed in Annex III of the Barcelona Convention, can still be easily spotted within the Güllük Gulf. These include, but are not limited to: *Maja squinado* (spider crab), *Epinephelus marginatus*, *Tonna galea*, *Chelonia mydas* – the last two species under protection by various international treaties. A more extensive listing is provided in Annex A.

Photo 7. Inceburun, Mandalya Gulf, empty fish feed boxes, excess extrude feed, and plastic bags washed ashore from the cages, September 2009. This is by now a daily occurrence. (Photos by Bikem Ekberzade).

Photo 8. Asin Gulf: *Posidonia oceanica* and *Pinna nobilis* (left); a *P. rudis* shell. (Photos by Bikem Ekberzade).

Chelonia mydas is one of the most important species found within the Güllük Gulf. While we think they use the Gulf as a resting and feeding spot during their migration, there is ample proof that the species is being adversely affected from pollution and the massive marine traffic which the aquaculture farms cause in the Gulf. During the few months in which this report was compiled, the corpses of at least 4 grown samples of this sensitive species has been washed ashore, their shells cracked and the bodies badly decomposed. The endangered *C. mydas*, which is currently under protection, can frequently be spotted within Asin and Mandalya inner gulfs during a period between mid-summer to mid-fall. Both the local residents and local fishermen have spotted this seclusive creature.

Photo 9. A dead loggerhead tangled in fish nets, washed ashore (left); a living individual (right). Both *C. mydas* and *C. caretta* frequent the Güllük Gulf. However their sightings are decreasing as the meadows retreat. (Photos by Bikem Ekberzade).

There is evidence that *C. mydas* uses the area as a feeding spot as the basin is still covered with *Posidonia* meadows, inhabiting several other species to which the mydas is a natural predator. We were able to secure the information of both *C. mydas* and the *Caretta caretta* entry into the Gulf, with help of satellite data provided to us by the kind help of Carribbean Conservation Corporation (CCC 1-2). When asked about the possible cause of death of the creatures, CCC staff told us that the deaths may have occurred due to pollution, getting tangled up in loose fishnets and suffocation. They also mentioned that the fact that the shells have been broken, may suggest that the animal has been run over by a fast moving marine vehicle post-mortem. Below, Marydele Donnelly, in one of our cross-correspondences provided some extremely useful information:

“The region once supported significant green turtle fisheries but today only 350-400 females nest each year in all of the Mediterranean (females do not nest annually so the entire nesting population is probably three times that size). As the situation has become so precarious for this species, every individual counts.”

Other species endemic to the region, such as sandbar sharks, are yet to be recorded live due to visibility limitations (underwater visibility in 2009 was 5m., whereas in 2010 it has dropped to below 1 meter in places hindering most observation efforts). However conversations with local fishermen point to the fact that these elusive animals are inhabiting the Gulf, yet keeping mainly to the spots where the cages are, for an easy catch.

Talking to Prof. Dr. Ali Cemal Gücü of METU, who specializes on the behaviour and habitats of the Mediterranean seal, we discovered that sandbar sharks have historically used the area around the antique city of Iasos and the cove of Kıyıkışlacık as their nursery, mostly due to its soft sedimentary basin, and naturally protected placement further inside the Asin Gulf. The locals from Kıyıkışlacık back this proposal, by sharing with us personal accounts of their "swim with the sharks" from their childhoods. In light of all this information, should a meticulous scientific study be undertaken on the biodiversity of the region, we are certain, several other sensitive and endangered species will be discovered. This hypothesis is also backed by Doç. Dr. Murat Bilecenoğlu of Adnan Menderes University, who, following skin dives in the region has declared that “the region is biologically more diverse than Fethiye Gulf, which is currently under protection.”

A dead specimen of *Rhinobatos cemiculus* was found in September 2010. It was washed ashore with its head severed and the body cast aside. This find sadly backs our concerns of the threats the sensitive species in the region face, especially prime predators, and by which means their population is being depleted.

Societal effects

Güllük Gulf is surrounded by small villages who traditionally make a living either through olive production or fishing. The introduction of aquaculture practices to the region largely disrupted the small-scale fishing practices. It was initially a welcome change as families started building makeshift farms along the coastline, as they would no longer have to venture out into the open sea. However, as these setups led to both organic and visual pollution, they soon were removed by local authorities, and those that didn't remove their farms were issued fines. However, this process deeply affected the fishing culture, as the coastal farms had deteriorated the fishing weir's marine ecosystem, and the native shrimps, catfish and other Crustaceans largely disappeared with the depletion of the seagrass meadows. The former fishermen, needing a steady income, were forced to start working at the fish farms. Once economically independent, they now became dependent on a meager monthly salary. The marine traffic within the gulf increased, as boats started carrying feed to the farms on a daily basis. The placement of the aquaculture farms soon became a center of conflict from another angle: the commercial traffic (large carriers, ships, sailboats, gulets (traditional wooden sailboats) started experiencing problems either due to the placement of the farms, or because of the armed guards that were now manning these farms. Most importantly, overtime, valuable local knowledge was lost, knowledge of building fishnets, sustainable hunting practices, native fishes, where and when to, and how to hunt, etc. Aside from the biodiversity that took a blow due to the unsustainable aquaculture practices throughout Güllük Gulf, local knowledge and the cultural ecosystem were also negatively affected.

What can be done

With a protection plan of participatory nature, involving the local communities and respecting local knowledge can extend a lifeline to the biodiversity of Güllük Gulf. This protection plan needs to define and administer fines to all centers of pollution whether they be land-based, or marine-based (aquaculture farms) indiscriminately. NGOs, whose constitutions prioritize nature restoration, preservation, protection should step in to step up the advocacy efforts, while scientists should participate directly in the monitoring of the Gulf for further threats, and identify the opportunities there

may lie for scientific research with a focus on preservation and protection. These steps can be taken in the medium-short term.

Monitoring projects for Mandalya and Asin Gulfs need to be started immediately, with the Ministry of Environment being a stakeholder in these projects, where scientific information can be relayed directly to the Ministry, who in turn can take appropriate action to curb the threats, and establish measures to deter the polluting bodies. This is a medium-long term strategy, with a potential for sustainability. At its final stage, an MPA/SPA (Marine Protected Area) status should be sought. Asin Gulf exhibits a structure suitable to SPAMI criteria developed in conjunction with the 1995 Barcelona protocol. In summary: the area has at least 2 antique cities, a protected area used by aquatic and migratory birds as a resting spot and nursery (Tuzla gölü ve havzası, a previous RAMSAR site). Once the greater Güllük Gulf becomes a protected area, local administrations and NGOs can run small to medium size projects with an ultimate aim to protect local livelihoods and indigenous knowledge, as well as the biodiversity of this important region. Supporting local cooperatives, establishing training centers, summer camps and eco-tourism could also provide alternatives for a sustainable human-nature coexistence in a fragile ecosystem.

Conclusion

This white paper aims to detail the observations of the past three years of the state of the marine habitats, and the effects of the commercial aquaculture practices inside Güllük Gulf. It provides a preliminary assessment of an important threat to the biodiversity of an otherwise vibrant semi-closed Gulf. There are three major polluters in the region. The primary polluter at the time of writing are the fish farms. However, the uncontrolled coastal urban expansion is also a potential threat to the health of the marine habitats, not to mention to terrestrial biodiversity in its environments. The third potential polluters are the commercial ships that may introduce non-native species to the Gulf through their balast water. However, this commercial sector is strictly monitored by the necessary administrations, and only under extreme cases, accidents, or intentional breach of legal restrictions, which end up in large fines and act as a potential deterrent.

The Gulf exhibits high levels of biodiversity. During the monitoring phase between 2007-2010, despite limited dives, an important initial list of taxa has been collated. With further participation of scientists working in related fields (marine biology, oceanography, etc.), and more detailed research, there is high potential that this list can be expanded as more species will be observed by trained eyes, and their presence recorded.

Photo 10. Asin Gulf, very turbid waters and a baby *Epinephelus marginatus*. (Photo by Bikem Ekberzade).

ANNEX A

PLANTAE

Underwater flora within Asin and Mandalya inner gulfs:

CHLOROPHYTA (observed around Inceburun)

- *Halimeda tuna*
- *Codium bursa*
- *Udotea petiolata*
- *Valonia utricularis*

CYANOPHYTA

- *Rivularia sp*

MAGNOLIOPHYTA

- *Halophila stipulacea* (endangered, threatened, under protec. Barcelona '95)
- *Posidonia ocanica* (endangered, threatened, under protec. Barcelona '95)
- *Zostera marina* (endangered, threatened, under protec. Barcelona '95)
- *Zostera noltii* (endangered, threatened, under protec. Barcelona '95)

PHAEOPHYTA (observed around Inceburun)

- *Padina pavonica*

RHODOPHYTA (observed around Inceburun)

- *Corallina elongata*
- *Corallina officinalis*
- *Jania rubens*
- *Lithophyllum*

ANIMALIA

Underwater fauna within Asin and Mandalya inner gulfs:

CNIDARIA (observed around Inceburun)

- *Actinia equina*
- *Anemonia sulcata*
- *Bunodactis verrucosa*
- *Cerianthus membranacea*
- *Cladocora caespitosa*

CRUSTACEA

- *Eriphia verrucosa*
- *Maja squinado* (under protec. Barcelona '95)

ECHINODERMATA (observed in both Asin and Mandalya inner gulf)

- *Astropecten* sp.
- *Echinaster sepositus*
- *Echinocardium cordatum*
- *Ophiothryx fragilis*
- *Sphaerechinus granularis*

MOLLUSCA (observed around Inceburun)

- *Anomia ephippium*
- *Arctica islandica*
- *Bittium reticulatum*
- *Bittium* sp.
- *Chlamys varia*
- *Columbella rustica*
- *Cytherae chione*
- *Gari fervensis*
- *Gibbula (Pseudodiloma) drepanensis*
- *Glycymeris* sp.
- *Holothuria forskåli*
- *Monodonta (Osilinus) turbinata*
- *Osilinus turbinatus*
- *Ostrea edulis*
- *Patella coerulea*
- *Patella* sp.
- *Patella vulgata*
- *Pinna nobilis* (endangered, threatened, under protec. Barcelona '95)
- *Pinna rudis*
- *Tonna galea* (endangered, threatened, under protec. Barcelona '95)

PORIFERA (observed around Inceburun)

- *Aplysina aerophoba* (endangered, threatened, under protec. Barcelona '95)
- *Chondrosia reniformis*

REPTILIA (marine)

- *Caretta caretta*
- *Chelonia mydas* (IUCN Redlist, endangered A2bd; endangered, threatened, under protec. Barcelona '95)

TELEOSTEI (observed around İnceburun)

- *Apogon imberbis*
- *Boops boops*
- *Chromis chromis*
- *Coris julis*
- *Dentex dentex*
- *Diplodus annularis*
- *Diplodus vulgaris*
- *Epinephelus marginatus* (IUCN Redlist, endangered A2d; exploitation regulated, under protec. Barcelona '95)
- *Gobius bucchichi*
- *Sarpa salpa*
- *Serranus scriba*
- *Sparus aurata*
- *Stephanolepis diaspros*

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